

TLCMap 2.0 - ARDC Platforms

End of Project Report

This report is intended to be published and made available via the project's webpage on the ARDC website (certain sections can be redacted if requested). Please write this report for an audience who are not already familiar with this project.

Project Information

1. Project Details:

Project title: TLCMap 2.0

Lead organisation: University of Newcastle

Other organisations involved in delivering the project: ANU, ECU, UNE, University of Melbourne, University of Sydney, WSU, Australian National Placenames Survey

Contact person name: Hugh Craig

Project start and end dates: 24 February 2021 to 31 January 2022

2. Background

Context and Project Aims

The Time-Layered Cultural Map of Australia platform (TLCMap; tlcmap.org) is a software platform meeting the digital mapping needs of humanities and social science researchers, from beginner to advanced. Development commenced in 2019. Two key features are the capacity to view change over time and the use of deep maps which combine multiple layers of data to visualise patterns and relationships in complex spatio-temporal and cultural materials. Development has been user driven with research projects as test cases, and attracting new researchers along the way. While there are well-developed stand-alone data archives for social and cultural research in Australia, the current TLCMap is unique in offering the means to find, visualise and interrogate historical and cultural data from diverse sources organised through spatio-temporal coordinates. It serves humanities and social science researchers who are interested in using spatio-temporal data by adding functionality focused on humanities and cultural needs not already available in STEM focused systems.

The aims of the TLCMap 2.0 project were to enhance the platform through improved connectivity to relevant external platforms and archives and to national placename authorities, and by adding new features in the handling of spatial and temporal data. TLCMap 2.0 aims to allow researchers to: search across spatio-temporally indexed data (eg: to ask "What's here?") in multiple data sources; search an Australian gazetteer including historical, indigenous and other placenames; use spatio-temporal tools to analyse and visualise layers without programming knowledge; incorporate registered public datasets with their own data workflows with simple import/export options as well as web services APIs; and provide a relatively easy means for humanities researchers to create engaging online digital maps. It aims to lower the barrier to entry for humanities and social science researchers through better pathways in the website, adding tutorials and documentation, and new

features matching the practices of the target user group.

3. Achievement of project aims:

Outline the project aims and how they were achieved.

The aim of the Project according to the Project Plan is to enhance the existing Time-Layered Cultural Map of Australia platform by

- 1 providing a spatio-temporal window to some existing large foundational humanities data sets, such as the Historical and Colonial Census Data Archive, AusStage, and The Prosecution Project
- 2 creating and integrating new data sets arising from Key User projects and other supported projects
- 3 adding new features in the handling of spatial and temporal data, such as a Map Finder index of all points in all registered data sets, a Quick Coordinates KML from CSV tool, and a Map to Text tool

Notes on the achievement of the three project aims:

- Aim 1 We geolocated some NSW and WA towns and municipalities and created a public data layer for TLCMap with their 1901 populations, with each record linked back to the online Historical and Colonial Census Data Archive. A layer of almost 500 geolocated corroborees from AusStage has been added to the Gazetteer, providing a good illustration of how institutional collections can be spatiotemporally indexed for discoverability and visualisation. We have a public data layer with geolocations and dates for Australian prisons derived from The Prosecution Project.
- Aim 2 A number of data sets have been added representing different humanities use cases, including large sets of computer-harvested data, biographical information with timelines, journey routes, and dated journeys – see below under Q14 and Q18. We anticipate continued growth in contributions as awareness of TLCMap and its capabilities spreads. The system has been designed to provide individual incentives to contribute, such as to create engaging visualisation, and create ‘non-traditional’ research outputs contributing to researcher’s profiles, to build towards the critical mass that will realise community benefit.
- Aim 3 (a) The Gazetteer of Historical Places was identified as the most useful and desirable part of TLCMap through user consultation and workshops. The word ‘Placenames’ in the title was renamed to ‘Places’ to reflect its dual role of enabling search of the most comprehensive and complete aggregate of placenames in Australia, and of being an ever-growing spatio-temporal index of places of cultural significance to Australia, accumulating through institutional, researcher and community contributed layers. In 2021 we focused efforts on an overhaul of the Gazetteer as the centrepiece of TLCMap which other systems would attach to. This included revising the underlying data structure; establishing and implementing a policy for unique identifiers and; simplifying, debugging, streamlining, and documenting the process for contributing to it; and the addition of visualisation options. Unlike many other systems, the Gazetteer enables search within and across layers, not just a search of metadata for layers. This focus of effort and improvement meant it has been easy for project partner researchers to add their data when ready, and it has attracted other early adopters to TLCMap.
- Aim 3 (b) The Quick Coordinates tool for quickly and easily adding coordinates to data to produce mappable data is now deployed after testing.

Aim 3 (c) In the event we had to defer work on the text-based aspects of TLCMap. This meant that previous work on enhancements to the Pelagios Recogito system for mapping texts could not be concluded. This and other ambitions remain should the opportunity arise to fulfil them.

4. Achievements against project work packages:

Record achievement of project work packages, including details of the deliverables, in the table below **or in a spreadsheet** if preferred.

Use the following criteria and colours to assign a status to each work package:

Status Key

Non-completion has no impact on outcome	Not yet completed, however, has no impact on project outcomes. Responsibility for completion has been assigned and agreed by the Steering Committee.
Non-completion has some impact on project outcomes	Not yet completed and non-completion may have some impact on the project outcomes. Delay has been accepted by the Steering Committee and responsibility for completion has been assigned.
Will not be completed and has impact on project outcomes	Will not be completed and has an impact on the project outcomes. The Steering Committee has accepted the non-completion and understands the impact to the project outcomes.
Completed	Completed.

Milestone / Deliverable / Work Package	Details including explanation of any variation (include links to relevant documentation)	Agreed Due Date	Actual Completion Date or Expected Completion Date	Status (highlight colour as per table above)
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M1 Contract Signing		End Feb	March	
M2 Project Plan	Approved project plan	End April	April	
1 Establish Data Provider Relations	Contact established with major data providers	End May	June	
2 Assess Data Provision	Licensing, feasibility and compliance with FAIR principles and TLCMap requirements assessed	End May	May	
3 Manage scope and UX	Management of feedback on the platform from Key Users and selected testers, bug fixes and feature requests	Ongoing	Continuous through the project	

4 Finalise sub-project plans	Formal agreements with each of 6 partners on sub-projects, and deliverables incorporated into the main project plan as an addendum	End May	July	
M3 Progress Report	Report detailing progress against agreed deliverables, FAIR, and impact	21 June	June	
5 TLCMap data sets requirements	Guidelines for formatting data sets to be indexed in TLCMap and published after user consultation	End June	July	
6 Automated dynamic data updates	Development of supervised automation for update of at least 1 dynamic major data provider, such as AusStage	End July	Not completed	
7 Core static data	Data preprocessing and spatiotemporal indexing for at least 3 large static datasets, such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bownern and AIATSIS language sets - Australian Census reports 1833-1901 - Australian Women's Register - The Prosecution Project 	End July	November	
8 Core system upgrades	Upgrades to systems for TLCMap data workflow for humanities researchers, especially in Map Finder (universal point indexing), Quick Coordinates (KML from CSV tool) and Map to Text (placenames in text detected and mapped alongside)	End August	Completed January 2022	'Map Finder' concept included in GHAP. Quick Coordinates now deployed. 'Map to Text' not completed.
Financial Statement	For the period up til 30 June 2021	30 Aug 2021	August	
9 Contribution UX	UX of community contribution interface upgraded	End September	January 2022	
10 Complete sub-projects	Sub-projects delivered to University of Newcastle team	End October	October	
11 System tweaks	Upgrades to systems for TLCMap data workflow, responding to feedback from sub-projects	End October	November	

12 Testing and debugging of Version 2.0	Tested fully functional version in production online	End November	December	
13 Documentation and Training Materials	Add to the existing documentation on tlcmap.org to detail the new functionality and interfaces developed by the Newcastle team and the partners, and policies such as privacy, crediting, linking, and permissions	End November	December	
14 Confirm compliance	Compliance with FAIR principles and TLCMap requirements confirmed	End November	November	
15 Researcher Projects	Integration of at least 3 researcher projects using core TLCMap tools	End December	December	
16 Community Contributions	Inclusion of at least 3 community contributions, such as <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - indigenous placenames and meanings of a region (such as Newcastle/Awabakal) - local historical society places of significance - features identified from old maps of the Royal Flying Doctor Service 	Mid December	Not completed	In the event we had to focus on the core user group of 'humanities researchers'. Wider engagement with community was deferred pending simplified and better documented contribution process.
17 Launch and promote	Media release, online launch, and other promotional events	Mid December		This had to be delayed till major upgrades had been completed. The platform is now ready for wider promotion.
M4 Final Report	Report on details of agreed deliverables, FAIR, and impact	Mid January		

Financial statement	For the entire project period	Two months after end of project (9 Feb 2022)		
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5. Issues/Challenges

Please list **significant** issues or challenges encountered during project delivery, using the following table or [link to an Issues register](#).

#	Date Opened	Description of Issue	Status Update / Description of resolution	Status	Date closed	Issue Owner
	<i>Date issue was opened</i>	<i>Provide a brief description of the issue</i>	<i>Provide an update of the status of the issue and/or note how the issue was resolved</i>	<i>Open Closed</i>	<i>Date issue was closed</i>	<i>Who is responsible for this issue?</i>
1	Beginning of project	TLCMap set out to work cooperatively in a broader software ecosystem, and to be a good digital citizen in contributing funds and effort to enhancements in cognate systems. However, although there was some successful collaboration and repurposing, and plenty of good will, in many cases hopes were not realised. The amount of time deserved by each relationship could not be given. Difficulty in meeting obligations of relationships and angst over resourcing and software choices proved a distraction. It was also difficult to navigate diverse modes of working among these partners, from	Collaboration could work better in future if the parties were not spread too thin across many activities. In future such relationships could be clearer in their ambition, more modest in their intended outcomes, and be joint grant applications. Interoperability remains an imperative for us, but could be more clearly and simply specified in terms of open standards, import/export, and web services APIs, and be more clearly articulated at the outset, with some allowance for testing and adjustment.	Open		System Architect and Project Lead

		<p>those who need substantial budgets to get commercial providers to do clearly defined and inflexible work packages, to open source communities, to those who get what they can get done when they can, and those who work on software almost as a hobby, to those who have a high level of commitment to solve anything thrown their way but suffer from burnout, especially in the context of the pandemic. Internal development with a small team was more successful by comparison.</p>				
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6. Project Acceptance

Have all the original needs of the stakeholders been met, and are there any ongoing concerns that need to be documented and/or addressed?

The core concerns and needs of stakeholders have been met but there are some expectations that we were unable to meet - in particular for spatio-temporal text processing. See Q 3. It is nonetheless understood by all stakeholders that the field of digital mapping in humanities is vast, with endless potential and that the needs of different disciplines are often quite diverse, across mapping mobility, text processing, virtual reality and so on. It is understood that only a small fraction of needs can be met and partners accept the efficacy of the TLCMap approach involving the ongoing collection of requirements, flexibility, prioritisation, and responding to real world researcher needs and feedback.

Several public datasets now in TLCMap are outcomes from partner projects: “Frederick Deeming” (see Q 15) (Prof R. Smith, ANU); “The NSW Aborigines Protection / Welfare Board 1883 - 1969: A History (ARC DP150100247)” (see Q 15) (Profs V Haskins and J Maynard, University of Newcastle); and “WALBS [Western Australian Legacies of British Slavery] bios – all” (<https://www.tlcmap.org/ghap/publicdatasets/169>) (Prof P Arthur, ECU). For these partners the activity also helped refine and clarify their research methodology in terms of the data needed and the structure it needed to be in to be able to map it in a meaningful and accessible way.

7. Sustainability plans

Please indicate what plans have been put in place for continued operation of the platform, and how these will be supported.

After discussions in the platform Advisory Group and Steering Committee in 2021, we have developed a four-pronged strategy for the sustainability of the platform.

I Keeping TLCMap available for public use and informing the user base (steady-state)

We are seeking commitment by the University of Newcastle (henceforth UON) for this in the first instance for:

- \$11,000 p.a. for hosting and maintenance –
 - \$8,000 p.a for hosting on a consumption model, i.e. outsourced to Amazon Web Services or similar (estimate courtesy of UON IT Business Partner); and
 - \$3,000 p.a to keep the platform operating (30 hours p.a. for a senior software engineer; or a combination of a senior software engineer and a student junior developer hired via the UON JobsOnCampus scheme) and
- 60 hours p.a. for the editing of a bi-monthly newsletter, as a contribution of hours from a UON College of Human and Social Futures professional staff member.

II Help for researchers and projects using a static TLCMap (cost recovery)

In this scheme, project support packages (20, 50 or 100 hours, \$2,000, \$5,000 or \$10,000) are organised up-front as commitments from a home institution, or itemised in a funded grant, but work is outsourced directly to a commercial provider. UON, or the local administering institution external to UON, enters into a contract with the provider. Issues are triaged by a manager within the provider into

- Procedural – skills transfer – help in using platform as is (e.g. which button to press) – work done by a graduate assistant
- Consulting – edit data, set up project, continuing guidance – work done by a PhD level employee
- Tech support – a bug that arises, a new issue – work done by a full stack developer
- Onboarding a large data set – work done by a PhD level employee
- Developing a new feature for a given project – work done by a senior developer

This is a cost-recovery model and requires no on-going funding. It is dependent on a stable provider with good corporate knowledge of the TLCMap code. Candidates would be Kotelliko (founded by a former student TLCMap developer) and Systemik Solutions (retained by the University of Sydney for a similar role).

III Major new software development

This would be funded by a LIEF or Linkage grant or other national competitive grant, and carried out by UON employees, or completed as in-kind by a partner in the grant in question. The next opportunity we are aware of is the 2022 LIEF round, for 2023 funding, for which we have registered a Notification of Intent with UON to apply.

IV TLCMap Consortium

This would broaden the support base for the platform. It would be the base for collaborative National Competitive Grant applications for major enhancements. It might also be a primary source for requests for the cost-recovery packages outlined above.

Candidates for partners include

- the universities of CIs listed in previous funding applications, successful and pending (ANU, Curtin, ECU, Flinders, UMelb, UNE, UniSA, USyd, UTS and WSU)
- Billie Virtual Labs, a First Nations social impact cultural design company with interests in presenting Australian cultural materials accessible through maps (Bill Pascoe as System Architect is working on a draft MOU with BVL)
- Prakaś Foundation, a Sydney-based non-profit association established to support digital scholarship in Buddhist studies and Sanskritic languages, and a partner in the Research Environment for Ancient Documents Workbench consortium, which has parallels with TLCMap in providing humanities research software as a service
- ARDC; Geosciences Australia; Australian National Placenames Survey; National Library of Australia; Australian Institute of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Studies; Hunter Writers Centre; Newcastle Museum

Partners would not commit to cash but to in-kind contributions, especially some FTE; to fostering TLCMap-based research and outreach projects; and to offering feedback on detailed and larger operational aspects of the platform. A minimum FTE commitment for each partner might be 0.2 FTE each year for five years (2022-6). There would be an annual on-line meeting of all partners and other consultations as required.

The Chair of the Consortium would come from outside UON but the Director would be appointed by UON.

Lessons learnt

8. What went well?

What positive lessons can be usefully applied to other projects? Did the ARDC support/partnership benefit the project's outcomes?

Governance

We had regular one-hour online meetings of an Advisory Board and a Steering Committee. They were an excellent source of advice in tactical and strategic matters and of contacts, connecting us to ARDC (see below) and to the wider worlds of eResearch, commercial IT, consultancies and digital project management. The current sustainability plan for the platform (see Q 7, above) draws on discussions in the Advisory Board and Steering Committee.

ARDC engagement

We were previously funded by ARC, which has strict standards of research conduct, requires progress and final reports, and monitors expenditure by the administering organisation closely, but otherwise does not engage with a project during the funded period. ARDC by contrast offered close engagement, including

- a representative on the TLCMap Steering Committee (Kerry Levett) who secured for us a code review by an ARDC staff member, and provided a contact in Geosciences Australia, resulting in a very helpful meeting with them;

- extensive sharing of best practice via COP sessions;
- organising a presentation including TLCMap at the eRA conference; and
- Informal networking with other ARDC-supported platforms, which led to our participation in fortnightly online Office Hours sessions.

In general, the informal exchanges of tacit knowledge resulting from engagement with ARDC were of great benefit in providing wider contexts for platform design and development.

Amplifying the reach of existing data sets

The TLCMap Gazetteer draws on a download of the Australian National Placenames Survey data set. In TLCMap the ANPS data (300,000 placenames) is made searchable and is more or less fully geolocated for the first time. In the course of the current project the TLCMap Gazetteer was identified as the centrepiece of TLCMap. Users remark that it has been the only means by which they have been able to find remote and historical places such as homesteads mentioned in old texts. Such places are not available through Google Maps and not readily discoverable in other sources. This demonstrates success in delivering specifically humanities needs and dealing with US and European bias in international services. Use of the web services API to the Gazetteer was essential for early adopter, Fiannuala Morgan (ANU), to develop a heuristic programme to geolocate 7,000+ instances of bushfires mentioned in Australian non-fiction. Her resulting dataset of bushfires in history has been contributed back to TLCMap as a layer.

TLCMap prompted the release of Australian historical census data (from the Historical and Colonial Census Data Archive: Australian Bureau of Statistics and Australian Data Archive) in more accessible forms. This is a core data set for Australian colonial history of interest to any historian in Australia, and was previously available for download but not for online query. The dataset has now been made more accessible on the web, and elements of it are now discoverable in TLCMap ,with links back to the online data set.

The availability of Tim Sherratt’s listing of geolocated places of publication of Trove newspaper articles through TLCMap saved possibly weeks of work for the research assistant working on the Deeming Project to produce their own dataset of 1591 places of publication of articles relating to the Deeming case in researching crime fiction in Australia.

9. What could be improved?

Are there lessons learnt that can usefully be applied to other projects? i.e.

- Were risks identified early enough and were mitigation strategies effective?
- Were there any issues that could have been avoided? If so, how?
- Could any issues/risks be avoided for future projects?
- Were there any changes to the project as originally planned? If so, are there any reflections or considerations which could be considered for future similar projects?
- How can ARDC’s support/partnership improve to meet the project’s needs?

Description	Impact on project	What was actioned/could be a solution(s) for future projects
Difficulties arose from competing work	Our principal software design and development capacity for the project was an 0.9 FTE System Architect. Full time employment for this individual	The other employer funded an extra month’s work (i.e. 0.8 FTE) to the TLCMap project in

pressures for an employee	was made up by 0.1 FTE working on another project. There was an emergency on this other project in the middle of the year and the individual was under exceptional pressure to devote disproportionate time and energy to it, to the detriment of work on TLCMap.	recognition (they extended the System Architect’s contract to the end of January 2022).
Delays in signing partner sub-contracts	The host institution asked partners in the project to sign specially prepared agreements undertaking to make expenditures to match their contributions as described in the application presented to ARDC. The partners took some time to do this, probably because they were more used to ARC practice, in which the administering organisation requires partners to transfer funds to them, and then in a second step returns the funds, often with a quantum of ARC funding on top.	After some negotiation, all the agreements were signed (the last being in July, into the third quarter of a four-quarter project). ARDC might spell out in the grant conditions what the ARDC expects in terms of arrangements for partner outlays for a project.

10. Anything else you would like to tell us about the project:

TLCMap in funding applications

The platform is now playing a part in research designs for new projects and platforms.

TLCMap is a partner in the two-year project led by the University of Melbourne to build an “Australian Cultural Data Engine for Research, Industry and Government”. This is funded by an ARC LIEF grant (LE210199921, \$440,000). The spatio-temporal mapping for the various data sets in the project will be provided by TLCMap. The ACD-Engine is an open software engineering facility that interacts with leading existing cultural databases in architecture, visual and performing arts, humanities, and heritage, with the aim of benefiting policy and planning and bringing new alignments between researchers, industry and government.

In September, 2021, Dr Mitchell Harrop was awarded a Publication Subsidy by the Australian Academy of the Humanities for an innovative guide to the digital humanities based on TLCMap.

TLCMap 2.0 Key User A/Prof Bill Palmer will develop an interface to integrate the language archive PARADISEC with TLCMap to add new spatio-temporal points of entry to the collection. The parent project, “Modularised cultural heritage archives – future-proofing PARADISEC”, is funded by a LIEF led by the University of Melbourne (LE220100010, \$620,000). This project will promote national and international research collaboration with Australian archiving communities and build capacity in Pacific cultural institutions, benefiting research data communities across the sector as well as community custodians of cultural heritage collections.

Dr Helen English has been awarded an ARC DECRA fellowship for 2022-5 on “Creative ageing through transformative engagement with music” (DE220100084, \$447,148). Her application includes funding in the first year of the grant for research assistants to create maps of music engagement with

TLCMap. The use of the platform in the project was commended in one of the assessors' reports on the application.

Large data set in the pipeline

The Colonial Frontier Massacre Map (<https://c21ch.newcastle.edu.au/colonialmassacres/map.php>), credited with changing Australians' view of their history, was the inspiration for TLCMap. A comprehensive data set drawn from the Massacre Map will be contributed as a public layer to TLCMap after the embargo arising from the launch of the latest version has been lifted on 14th March 2022.

FAIR

11. FAIR Project Outputs

Describe how the **project** outputs (publications, documentation, code, etc) have been made FAIR, with particular focus on any reuse or potential for reuse of outputs beyond the original purpose.

TLCMap enables and encourages humanities researchers to produce FAIR data. The platform is primarily useful for open data, and making it publicly accessible. Datasets or 'layers' are assigned unique identifiers. Much attention was given to the best policy for assigning unique identifiers to individual 'places' within layers (ie: records/rows/entities) that would enable scalable expansion while avoiding various pitfalls and addressing certain needs. TLCMap IDs are auto incremented, case insensitive, base 16 numbers. They are both human and computer friendly, their uniqueness is easily implemented maintained, they can scale well beyond the expected amount of data, and they avoid containing accidental swear words in English.

Interoperability using open standards has proved an excellent strategy for development within TLCMap across many different development streams.

The Gazetteer, which is the centrepiece of TLCMap around which other systems are developed, has been built from the beginning with the intention of making all searches and queries available through a web services API. It is documented here: <https://tlcmap.org/guides/ghap/#ws> This RESTful web service enables both:

- External applications, or researchers code to search the Gazetteer, retrieve data, and access community contributed layers.
- Human users can easily copy links to share their information.

Data can be both ingested and output in open standard and easy to use formats, CSV, KML and GeoJSON.

This means that any user contributing data automatically abides by FAIR principles.

Web applications such as visualisations focus on use of GET parameters for user defined variables to ensure users can easily share their custom maps, and to ensure external applications can easily integrate with them simply by constructing a URL to pass in parameters in the URL query string.

Note: TLCMap is not an official repository and is dependant on external funding, so we cannot guarantee the longevity of records. For these reasons, although we place a high priority on assigning

unique identifiers, TLCMap is not an appropriate entity for minting DOIs. Our recommendation is that researchers should use data created for and generated by TLCMap to create archives and obtain DOIs from official research data repositories that provide long term assurance of sustainability. TLCMap recommends use of ROCrate and Arkisto for this purpose and would like to more closely integrate with this open standard more in future.

12. Implementing FAIR Platforms

Describe how the Platform itself is FAIR, with particular focus on any reuse or potential for reuse of platform components beyond the original purpose (if this is not already described in Section 11).

The platform and components are, in principle, open source, and repositories exist for each system and subsystem in Bitbucket.

The TLCMap platform has an open-source approach to software development and depends greatly on other open-source systems. However, many of the systems are focused on user interfaces and visualisations and as a platform that hopes to aggregate information, it makes less sense for the software to proliferate. Most of the systems are unlike typical research software, which offers a method, or a library, for performing certain functions and is thus most appropriately shared in repositories for re-use by others to maximise benefits of their development.

Also, providing access to all the code and database structure may be a security risk and, as the platform grows, there will be a lot of people's data dependant on it. For this reason, while the platform strongly promotes FAIR principles (see Q 11), we don't promote re-use of the code for the platform itself.

Nonetheless the data is in a repository, so could easily be repurposed for use in other countries, or taken up by another institution.

13. Implementing FAIR-enabling Platforms

Describe what functions/features have been implemented in the Platform to enable FAIR outputs (i.e. how are data, code, visualisations, etc produced or processed by the Platform made FAIR/FAIRer).

Anyone may freely access data contributed by researchers through:

- Easy to use web interface
- Easy to access download of the data in open standard and familiar formats (CSV spreadsheet, KML, GeoJSON)
- Web services API to search and access metadata and records.

Users contributing data layers automatically, and with minimal effort, make their data available by the above means, so automatically, and simply, abide by FAIR principles.

Users contributing data layers are encouraged to fill in metadata and the time of contribution, and can easily return to fill in more details later.

Project Impact

The Government wishes to demonstrate the impact on researchers (and industry and the general public) of the NCRIS investment, and the ARDC Board is particularly concerned with being able to demonstrate the value of the investment in Research Platforms.

ARDC realises that a number of possible impact metrics are lag indicators.

Platform impact metrics

Impact metric (*add relevant details/links in next section)	Progress report 1	Progress report 2	Progress report 3	Progress report 4	PROJECT TOTAL
Number of datasets published (preferably with record in Research Data Australia)*					34 total; 13 with >100 records (see Q 15)
Number of publications using data generated by platform*					7
Number of publications that cite /reference the platform*					1
Social media mentions of platform*					Not collected
Blog posts/news articles that reference platform*					7
Number of users*					Contributors: 12 Visitors: 2352 (according to Google Analytics)
Number of active users (over 90-day period)					According to Google analytics: 551 Users 5350 Page views over 90 days.
Number of jobs run (i.e. number of processes submitted through the Platform)					NA
Instruments supported					NA
Number of engagement/outreach					11

activities (e.g. seminars, presentations, demos, meetings with new stakeholders)*					
Number of researchers trained (online or face-to-face)*					Estimated: 30
Availability of the platform (days in operation vs days offline)					100%

15. Links to publications and other communications

Published datasets generated by platform

Date	Link to a metadata record <i>or</i> Citation with DOI
20/06/2021	https://www.tlcmmap.org/ghap/publicdatasets/102 1901 NSW town populations (353 records)
23/01/2022	https://www.tlcmmap.org/ghap/publicdatasets/170 19 th Century Australian Bushfire Reporting (7454 records)
26/11/2021	https://www.tlcmmap.org/ghap/publicdatasets/112 Aboriginal Port Stephens (1826) (140 records)
15/02/2021	https://www.tlcmmap.org/ghap/publicdatasets/81 AustLang (440 records)
17/02/2021	https://www.tlcmmap.org/ghap/publicdatasets/84 Australian Prisons (204 records)
15/02/2021	https://www.tlcmmap.org/ghap/publicdatasets/80 Chirila Australian Language Locations (679 records)
27/01/2022	https://www.tlcmmap.org/ghap/publicdatasets/171 Corroborees in AusStage (488 records)
16/21/2021	https://www.tlcmmap.org/ghap/publicdatasets/159 Frederick Deeming (1591 records)
01/12/2021	https://www.tlcmmap.org/ghap/publicdatasets/154 Japanese POW Camps, World War II (533 records)
08/10/2021	https://www.tlcmmap.org/ghap/publicdatasets/135 Moravian Settlements – test (313 records)
26/11/2021	https://www.tlcmmap.org/ghap/publicdatasets/150

	Northern Territory Stock Routes, 1956 (180 records)
16/02/2021	https://www.tlcmmap.org/ghap/publicdatasets/82 The NSW Aborigines Protection / Welfare Board 1893-1969; A History (ARC DP 150100247) (332 records)
25/11/2021	https://www.tlcmmap.org/ghap/publicdatasets/140 Trove Newspaper Publication Locations (1879 locations)

Publications using data generated by platform

Date	Citation with DOI
24 June 2021	Fiannuala Morgan, "Geo-locating Real and Fictional Place: Analysis of Bushfires in Australian Literature and Newspaper Articles." National School of Arts Winter Seminar Series: Teaching and Researching in the Digital Humanities.
26 Nov 2021	Fiannuala Morgan, "Bushfire Literature and Reporting: Mythology, Memorialisation and Omission: An Analysis of Bushfire Reporting and Fiction in 19th Century Australian Newspapers." Graduate Digital Research Fellows Talk, Resbaz, Queensland
21-23 July 2021	Fiannuala Morgan, "Historical Fires Near Me." Texts and Their Limits, Victoria University
17 December 2021	Jasper Ludewig, "Mapping the Global Moravian Network: Progress, Method, Methodology", <i>Architectures of Order</i> Fellow Lecture, recording available at https://architecturesoforder.org/en/event/mapping-the-global-moravian-network-progress-method-methodology/
18 January 2022	Fiannuala Morgan, "Mythologised, Memorialised Then Forgotten: A History of Australia's Bushfire Reporting." The Conversation. http://theconversation.com/mythologised-memorialised-then-forgotten-a-history-of-australias-bushfire-reporting-170778 .
Forthcoming	P. Arthur and I. Smith, "Digital Representations of Slavery in Australia: Navigating Heritage, Identity and Power"
Forthcoming	P. Arthur and I. Smith, "Human Journeys in the Digital Age: Advances in Digital Historical Migration Studies"

Publications that cite/reference the platform

Date	Citation with DOI
2020	Arthur, P. L., E. Champion, H. Craig, N. Gu, M. Harvey, V. Haskins, A. May, B. Pascoe, A. Piper, L. Ryan, R. Smith and D. Verhoeven (2020). "Time-layered cultural map of Australia." Proceedings of the Digital Humanities in the Nordic Countries 5th Conference. S. Sanita Reinsone, I. Inguna Skadiņa, B. Anda and J. Daugavietis, Central Europe Workshop Proceedings. 2612: 184-191.

Social media mentions of the platform

Date	Link
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Example: July 2020	https://twitter.com/AusBiocommons/status/1251724453173538817?s=20
	Not collected

Blog posts/news articles that reference the platform

Date	Link
September 2021	https://humanities.org.au/our-community/recipients-of-the-2021-publication-subsidy-scheme/ Dr Mitchell Harrop, AAH Publication Subsidy, <i>Grimoire for the Digital Humanities: The Forbidden Atlas</i> (approach via “recipes” or “spells” and based on TLCMap)
June 2021	https://tgd.global/journal/tgd-good-design-awards
June 2021	https://good-design.org/projects/from-tech-centred-to-user-focused-a-transformed-humanities-research-platform/
June 2021	https://www.design.org.au/news/the-growth-drivers-win-exclusive-design-institute-of-australia-award-at-the-australian-good-design-awards
June 2021	https://www.ecovoice.com.au/the-growth-drivers-announced-as-winner-of-the-2021-australian-good-design-awards-design-institute-of-australia-award/
June 2021	https://ardc.edu.au/news/culture-mapping-tool-wins-national-award/
June 2021	https://tgd.global/journal/putting-the-human-back-in-humanities

16. Details on engagement, outreach and training activities

Activity	Activity description	No. of participants	Date of activity
UQ Digital Research Fellowship scheme	10-week internship in the platform, with fortnightly consultations, for an ANU PhD student, Fiannuala Morgan, resulting in the Bushfire data layer and publications	1	April-May 2022

UTS Digital Histories Workshop	'Time-layered Cultural Map: Mapping Tools for the Humanities in Australia'	30	13 May 2022
Meeting with new stakeholders	ECU partners met with researchers from Western Australian Legacies of British Slavery (WALBS) ARC project to discuss potential use of TLCMap in illustrating and analysing biographical data emerging from WALBS project	6	13 May 2021
University of Adelaide Digital Humanities Lab	'Mapping and the Humanities'	25	May 2022
Australian Catholic University workshop	'Teaching and Research in DH: Translating Places and Digital Mapping' [Feedback from the organiser, A/Prof Maggie Nolan: "I just wanted to thank you for your wonderful seminar yesterday. It was great to see what you are doing with TLC, to have it framed theoretically, and to open up the possibilities for what we could do with our students in semester 2. It's a fantastic project, with so much potential. Thank you for sharing it with us." "Gosh, I can't tell you what an awesome response I have had to this seminar series."]	~10	July 2021
University of Frankfurt workshop (Architectures of Order, LOEWE Research Cluster)	'Spatial Orders: An Introduction to the Digital Humanities' with guest speakers: Keith McClelland University College London Legacies of British Slave Ownership Jennifer Debenham The University of Newcastle Frontier Massacres Map Andrew Leach The University of Sydney The Architecture of Property Bill Pascoe The University of Newcastle Centre for 21st Century Humanities https://architecturesoforder.org/en/event/spatial-orders-an-introduction-to-the-digital-humanities/	~10	1 July 2021
Session at eRA conference	Paper in the BoF session on 'The Incredible Journey: Building capability to increase uptake of digital research infrastructure in Humanities, Arts, Social Sciences and Indigenous research practice'	~75	11 October 2021
Online Office Hours consultations hosted by QUT	With representatives from Time Layered Cultural Map, Australian Digital Observatory, Australian Text Analytics Platform and Language Data Commons of Australia, the office hours are a regular opportunity for students to consult and an opportunity for DH practitioners in	~6 at each session	12 and 26 October, 9 and 23 November, December

Digital Observatory	different parts of the country to 'talk shop'. https://research.qut.edu.au/digitalobservatory/office-hours/		7, 2021; 18 January 2022
Meeting with Geosciences Australia	Discussion of the relationship between the Geosciences Australia Composite Gazetteer and the TLCMap Gazetteer	4	27 September 2021
Dissemination of platform content	ECU partners shared data and content being used for the TLCMap platform with researchers from the Western Australian Legacies of British Slavery (WALBS) ARC project team	8	19 December 2021
Presentation of platform	ECU partners presented to the Western Australian Legacies of British Slavery (WALBS) ARC project team the uploaded WALBS biographical data content in TLCMap Gazetteer of Historical Australian Places	8	Mid-January 2022

17. Details on users of the platform

If possible, provide a brief breakdown of where these users come from; for example, which institutions the core user groups are from, or how many users from each of the following broad categories: .edu.au, .gov.au, .org.au, .edu (international academic institutions), .com (gmails etc.), other.

Organisation type	Number of users
.edu.au	Contributing users: 100% Visiting users are overwhelmingly from Australia.
.gov.au	
.org.au	
.edu	
.com	
other	

18. Impact stories

Please detail any research impacts or highlights here. Other impacts could include outcomes of industry collaborations, platform community activities leading to new policy or practice, etc. Stories from users of the platform are particularly useful.

In 2021 TLCMap was named a Good Design Award Gold Winner for Educational Services, recognising the work done with consultants to re-design the platform and make it “user-focused” rather than “tech-centred”. This external recognition for the platform brought attention to its open-access, FAIR aspirations, and attracted new users. See the links in Q 15, above (under “Blog Posts / News Articles”).